

Enabling Local Multimodal AI for Metadata Generation in Archival Collections

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Abstract. Large-scale digitisation has transformed access to archives, but generating reliable metadata remains a bottleneck. This short study explores whether locally deployed open-source multimodal models can assist archivists by generating descriptive metadata based on the “Four Ws” (*Who, What, Where, When*). We implement a proof-of-concept using **Qwen**, supported by GPT-assisted curation of Winston Churchill images, and evaluate its potential for integration into digital catalogues.

Keywords: Multimodal learning; metadata generation; archives; digital heritage; Qwen; EU AI Act.

1 Introduction

Digitisation initiatives such as Europeana [4] and the Digital Public Library of America (DPLA) [2] have expanded access to cultural heritage, but metadata creation remains slow and inconsistent. Manual cataloguing requires domain expertise and is difficult to scale, especially in large archives of images and moving media. Integrating vision and language models offers a potential solution, automating descriptive tasks like captioning, identification, and temporal or spatial inference. For archive owners and curators, reliance on cloud-based models raises potential risks related to protection of intellectual property (IP) and compliance with the EU AI Act [1], which prohibits certain biometric categorisation systems. This study investigates whether an open-source model (**Qwen**) can be deployed locally to generate catalogue-ready metadata using the archival “Four Ws” framework.

2 Institutional Context

Reach plc: Commercial publisher with ~200M images, mostly undigitised. Key considerations: protection and preservation of IP.
National Gallery: 2.5k paintings and 40k digitised images, with well-structured metadata. Interest: sitter recognition and discovery tools.
BFI: 19 PB moving-image archive, including film, television, and special collections. Includes IP owned by third parties, which prompts legal and ethical considerations around reliance on cloud-based models. Needs: exploratory search, identity tracking, and open-source compliance.

3 Methodology

We propose **FOURW-QWEN**, a pipeline designed for lightweight deployment within archival workflows.

Dataset Curation—We curated 16 Winston Churchill images without labels or metadata to serve as a pilot. These images represent common archival challenges: historical figures, varied contexts, and absent metadata.

Four-W Extraction—A GPT model was prompted with visual Q&A tasks to extract the Four Ws: *Who*: identity; *What*: activity or event; *Where*: geographical or institutional setting; *When*: temporal context (date/era). This framework was selected because the Ws—strictly the Five Ws, with the addition of ‘why’—is a foundational method used by archivists and researchers to obtain structured and searchable image metadata. The outputs were encoded into structured catalogue entries.

Model Selection and Deployment—We selected **Qwen-VL** [3], an open-source vision-language model. Fine-tuned with the curated metadata, it was deployed on-premises using a simple Streamlit interface.

Workflow Integration—The system returns structured metadata plus a free-text description. Curators can accept, edit, or reject fields. This “human-in-the-loop” design aligns with archival standards such as Dublin Core and CIDOC-CRM. For this study, the user enters a prompt along with an image and gets a description guided by the Four Ws.

Figure 1: (Top) GPT-assisted Four-W encodings, demonstrating the visual Q and A concept. (Bottom) Qwen inference producing catalogue-ready metadata. The left in colab and the right our lightweight frontend gui

4 Qualitative Findings

The proof-of-concept shows:

- GPT Q&A can bootstrap metadata from unlabeled images.
- Qwen generates descriptions aligned with cataloguing practices (see Fig. 1).
- Local deployment reduces institutional concerns about IP exposure.

5 Conclusion

FOURW-QWEN demonstrates that open-source multimodal AI can be adapted for archival metadata generation while safeguarding IP and compliance. Though limited to a small qualitative study, the approach shows promise for scaling across archives. Future work will extend to larger datasets, cross-referencing with text archives, and curator-led evaluation.

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